

Vesica piscis in puzzles on Sangaku, the Japanese calculation tablets

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna
Politecnico di Torino

On Sangaku, that is on Japanese "calculation tablets" of the Edo period, we can find geometric puzzles concerning a type of geometric figure, which is today known as "vesica piscis". Here we discuss some puzzles and their solutions.

Introduction

Sangaku means "calculation tablet" and contains Japanese geometrical problems. Calculation wooden tablets were placed as offerings at Shinto shrines or Buddhist temples during the Edo period¹. This was a period of isolation in the history of Japan, during which the Japanese mathematicians developed their own "traditional mathematics". According to [1], in the 1850s, the Japanese mathematics began giving way to Western methods. The script in which mathematics was written changed and, as a result, today few people know how to understand the historic tablets (see [1,2] and references therein, and also [3-6]).

A web site, www.wasan.jp/index.html or www.wasan.jp/english/, is dedicated to the Japanese tradition of mathematics, or Wasan, by Hiroshi Kotera. The site provides a list of Wasan based on Prefectures. Let us choose, for instance, the Yamagata Prefecture. The list provides many images showing wooden tablets with several puzzles on them. Let us consider www.wasan.earth.linkclub.com/yamagata/haguro3.png.

1 The Edo period or Tokugawa period lasted from 1603 to 1868 in the history of Japan. In that period Japan was under the rule of the Tokugawa shogunate and the country's 300 regional daimyō. The Edo period was characterized by economic growth. It was based on strict social order and on isolationist foreign policies. Being a period of peace, people had the possibility to enjoy arts and culture. The shogunate was officially established in Edo (now Tokyo) on March 24, 1603, by Tokugawa Ieyasu. The period came to an end with the Meiji Restoration on May 3, 1868, after the fall of Edo.

The image shows a puzzle, here proposed in the Figure 1, adapted from the courtesy image given by the web site.

Figure 1 - Courtesy www.wasan.jp

Actually, we have two larger circles, intersecting each other. The circles are represented by the same kanji 大 which means "big", "large"². One of the circle has inside the kanji 圓 which means "circle".

Being represented by the same symbol, let us suppose that the two larger circles possess radiuses with the same length. The intersection is forming a geometrical figure that today, in the West, is known as "vesica piscis". In Latin, "vesica piscis" literally means "bladder of a fish". Let us note that the figure is also known as "mandorla", the Italian word for "almond". In fact, the term "mandorla" was used long before the term "vesica piscis"

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_kanji_by_stroke_count

appeared in an article published in 1820 about the architecture of the Middle Ages [7].

Therefore, on Sangaku, we can find geometric puzzles concerning the "vesica piscis". Here we will discuss some puzzles and their solutions.

Puzzle n.1

The first case that we propose is that depicted in the Figure 1.

Besides the larger circles, in the Figure, we see six smaller circles, with the same two *kanji* , that is 中 "middle", "medium", and the kanji 圓, that we have already seen, which means "circle".

Let us imagine a possible geometrical puzzle concerning Figure 1.

Usually, when we consider a "vesica piscis", we assume that the circles are intersecting in such a way that the centre of each circle lies on the circumference of the other. In this case, we should have a geometry as given in the following figure.

Figure 2

However, this is not the puzzle in the Figure 1, which is more complex. We have to consider also the square. The geometry is given in the following Figure 3.

Figure 3

The text and the solution of the puzzle is given in the "Sacred Mathematics: Japanese Temple Geometry" by Hidetoshi Fukagawa and Tony Rothman. It is the problem number 13 in the book [5]. It was proposed by Aotsuka Naomasa for the Dewasanzan shrine.

"Two large intersecting circles of radius R are inscribed as given in the Figure. Six smaller circles of equal radius r are inscribed in the large circles as shown. Two circles of radius t touch the square as well as the large circles. Find r in term of t ."

Answer:
$$r = \frac{0.4 t}{\sqrt{0.4+3-\sqrt{4(\sqrt{0.4+2})}}}$$

Figure 4

Let us consider p as the distance from the centre of either of the large circles having radius R to the point where the large circle is tangent to one of the small circles having radius r . We have that:

$$(R-r)^2=r^2+p^2 \quad ; \quad (R+r)^2=r^2+(3p)^2$$

Solving these two equations, we can find: $r=\frac{2}{5}R$; $p=\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}R$.

From Figure 4, we can see that the diagonal of the square is:

$$|AC| = 2\sqrt{2}R + 2p = (2\sqrt{2} + 2/\sqrt{5})R$$

Figure 5

We can also see from the Figure 5, that

$$|AD| = R + t + d = R + t + 2\sqrt{Rt} = (\sqrt{R} + \sqrt{t})^2$$

$$d^2 = (t + R)^2 - (R - t)^2 = 4tR$$

$$|AC| = \sqrt{2}|AD|$$

These two equations give: $\left(\frac{2\sqrt{10}+2}{\sqrt{5}}\right)R = \sqrt{2}(\sqrt{R}+\sqrt{t})^2$

Solving [5]: $t = \left(\sqrt{2+2/\sqrt{10}}-1\right)^2 \frac{5}{2}r$.

Another root exists but it does not match with the figure. So we have:

$$t = \left(\sqrt{2+2/\sqrt{10}-1} \right)^2 \frac{5}{2}r = \left(3+\sqrt{0.4}-2\sqrt{2+\sqrt{0.4}} \right) \frac{5}{2}r$$

$$r = \frac{0.4t}{(\sqrt{0.4+3}) - \sqrt{4(\sqrt{0.4+2})}}$$

Figure 6

Puzzle n.2

In [8,9], we can find a vesica piscis as usually defined, that is formed by the intersection of two circles with the same radius, intersecting in such a way that the centre of each circle lies on the circumference of the other (some geometry of this figure have been studied in [10,11]).

The author of [8,9], Rosalie Hosking tells about the problem sketched by the Figure 6, coming from the Kijimadaira Tenman-gū tablet. The problem deals with finding the diameter of a circle within a configuration of overlapping circles.

Figure 7

Let us assume that $2R=1$ be the diameter of the largest circle. We have $2r=0.5$, the diameter of the medium circle. Then, from the Figure 7:

$$|AB| = 2r+d \quad ; \quad d=\sqrt{0.5}-0.5$$

The diameter of the smallest circle is: $d=\sqrt{0.5}-0.5=0.2071067\dots$

In [9], we can find a transcription of the tablet. The statement of the problems is: as we can see in the diagram, there are two large circles and five medium circle. In the space between, there are small circles. Assume that the diameter of the large circle is 1 *shaku*. What is the diameter of the small circles? Answer: 2 *sun* and 0 7 *bu* ... (approximated).

In [8], it is told that dots ... represent an approximation and in [9] we can find that: 1 *shaku* = 10 *sun* = 100 *bu* = 1000 *rin* = 10000 *mo*. Therefore, the solution given above is the solution of the problem: $d=0.2071067\dots=2 \text{ sun } 0 7 \text{ bu } \dots$

Figure 8

Puzzle n.3

Another problem that we can find in [9] is the Kumakabuto Arakashihiko Second Problem. Let us stress that in this case, the vesica piscis is a generic one, as in the first puzzle that we have studied.

There is a large circle. Two medium circles are internally touching the large circle horizontally. Furthermore there are four small circles of equal size as in the figure [9]. The diameter of the large circle is 10 *sun*. Problem is: what are the diameters of the medium and small circles?

The answer is that the diameter of the small circle is 1 *sun* 8 *bu* 6 *rin* 1 *mo* 40666. The diameter of the medium circle is 6 *sun* 8 *bu* 6 *rin* 1 *mo* 406616.

Figure 9

Let us assume $|AD|=R$, the radius of the largest circle. From the Figure 9:

$$|AB|=R-r_m \quad ; \quad |AC|=R-r_s \quad ; \quad |BC|=r_m+r_s$$

However: $R=2r_m-2r_s$ and therefore: $|AB|=2r_m-2r_s-r_m=r_m-2r_s$

$$(r_m+r_s)^2=(r_m-2r_s)^2+(R-r_s)^2$$

$$4r_s^2-6r_m r_s+R^2-2r_s R=0 \quad ; \quad r_m=\frac{R}{2}+r_s$$

We have to solve equation: $2r_s^2+5Rr_s-R^2=0$.

Then, the diameters of the small and medium circles are:

$$2r_s=\frac{\sqrt{33}-5}{4}2R = 1 \text{ sun } 8 \text{ bu } 6 \text{ rin } 1 \text{ mo } 406616$$

$$2r_m=R+2r_s = 6 \text{ sun } 8 \text{ bu } 6 \text{ rin } 1 \text{ mo } 406616$$

Figure 10

Puzzle n.4

Figure 10 shows a Sangaku from the web site www.cut-the-knot.org by Alexander Bogomolny. Here, we have a conventional vesica piscis, formed by the intersection of two circles with the same radius, intersecting in such a way that the centre of each circle lies on the circumference of the other.

From the Figure 10 we have: $AB = \rho + 2r$; $OA = r$; $OH' = 3r = R$;
 $OB = 3r - \rho$

$$OB^2 + OA^2 = AB^2 \text{ gives : } \rho = 3r/5 = R/5$$

Figure 11

Puzzle n. 5

At the link www.wasan.jp/iwate/chibatanehide2.html, we can see a monument placed in the Hanaizumi Town Hall, Iwate Prefecture. On it, we can note the presence of a geometrical problem, reproduced from Chiba's Sampō Shin.sho, a large compendium of mathematics of 1830. It

was a bestseller with many editions, even in the Meiji era. The web page provides Ref.12. The image given in the Figure 11 reproduces the problem. The statement of the problem is the following:

甲円と丙円の直径が与えられたとき，乙円の直径を問う Given the diameters of 甲 circle and 丙 circle, find the diameter of 乙 circle.

$$OA=R-r \quad ; \quad OB=R-r' \quad ; \quad AB=r+r' \quad ; \quad 2R=4r-2\rho$$

$$AB^2=OA^2+OB^2 \rightarrow (r+r')^2=(R-r)^2+(R-r')^2$$

r, ρ are given and, therefore, R is known.

$$r'=R \frac{2R-2r}{2R+2r} = R \frac{2r-2\rho}{6r-2\rho}$$

For a history of Japanese mathematics, see please Ref.13.

Appendix

Let us consider the Figure 2. What is the radius of the small circle?

Given the frame of reference, let us write the equation of circles:

$$(x - R/2)^2 + y^2 = R^2 \quad ; \quad x^2 + (y - r_s)^2 = r_s^2$$

Solving the system of equations we have: $r_s = 3R/8$.

$$x^2 - xR + y^2 = 3R^2/4 \quad ; \quad 2yr_s = x^2 + y^2$$

Substituting:

$$y^2 \left[1 + \frac{4r_s^2}{R^2} \right] - 5yr_s + \frac{9}{16}R^2$$

The two circles have to be tangent: $25r_s^2 - \frac{9}{4}R^2 \left(1 + \frac{4r_s^2}{R^2} \right) = 0$.

Then: $r_s = 3R/8$

References

- [1] Weisstein, Eric W. Sangaku Problem. From MathWorld - A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/SangakuProblem.html>
- [2] Kimberling, C. (2006). Traditional Japanese mathematics problems of the 18th and 19th centuries; Japanese temple geometry problems San Gaku. The Mathematical Intelligencer 28, 61–63. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02987007>
- [3] Fukagawa Hidetoshi & Dan Pedoe (1989). Japanese temple geometry problems. Sangaku. Winnipeg: Charles Babbage. ISBN 9780919611214; OCLC 474564475

- [4] Fukagawa Hidetoshi and Dan Pedoe. (1991) How to resolve Japanese temple geometry problems? Tōkyō: Mori Kitashuppan. ISBN 9784627015302; OCLC 47500620
- [5] Fukagawa Hidetoshi, and Tony Rothman (2008). Sacred Mathematics: Japanese Temple Geometry. Princeton: Princeton University Press. ISBN 069112745X
- [6] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina and Baldi, Mauro Maria, Japanese Temple Geometry: A Digital Sangaku About a Regular Pentagon and the Golden Ratio (September 8, 2016). SSRN. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.2836615
- [7] Amelia Carolina Sparavigna. A discussion of a geometric shape that became a symbol known as mandorla or vesica piscis, starting from a Pythagorean point of view. 2020. HAL: hal-03112891. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4298852
- [8] Hosking, R. (2017). Solving Sangaku With Traditional Techniques. arXiv preprint arXiv:1701.08815.
- [9] Rosalie Hosking (2016). Sangaku: A Mathematical, Artistic, Religious, and Diagrammatic Examination. PhD Thesis of the University of Canterbury.
- [10] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina. (2020, November 25). The Vesica Piscis (Mandorla) and the Geometry of the Square Roots. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4290813>
- [11] Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina, & Baldi, Mauro Maria. (2016). A Mathematical Study of a Symbol: The Vesica Piscis of Sacred Geometry. PHILICA, (560). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4288186>
- [12] Japan Academy ed. (1959). History of Mathematics in Japan before the Meiji Era. Tokyo: Iwanami Shoten
- [13] Smith, D. E, & Mikami, Y. (1914). A history of Japanese mathematics. Chicago, The Open court publishing company.